

The Searching for the Mumbai & Zhejiang province cities GDP and the Chinese top cities GDP analysis Sustainably through Observing Statistic Value

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ABSTRACT: The nations & regions GDP (gross domestic product) will represent their comprehensive strength in views of economy level and quality, so searching it may have an important effectiveness for us to process statistic with the national producing amount every month, season and year. In the meantime, the value with y-y has also a significant meaning that reflects the economy growth step because we should clarify the increasing change so as to evaluate the increasement and declination value preciously. The positive y-y value may mean the good and rapid economy developing status whilst the minus one may state the bad and slow economy step. So we judge the economy developing enhancement and decrease through that y-y value for a certain period. Meantime, the toughness of national economy developing force will be shown by the y-y value because some regions remained a low economy situation but its y-y value had high one explained the high toughness with such regions besides the low GDP value. So that the new-quality productivity will be sought by us continuously special by those scientist, senior engineer, experts because they can lead to new feasible energy and dynamic force to drive the new one into realizing new-quality productivity producing a certain

effectiveness to GDP enhancement as last. In the meantime, the new-high-technology product will be formed accordingly that can create the industrial chains to support the high-knowledge skill transformed into the more comprehensive and complicated product for the sake of serving our citizen with modernization. The emerging technology would be driven the new energy force that includes the low -carbon and low-contamination electricity generator which may form the new quality productivity protected our earth from carbon-oxide and nitric-oxide etc. release. So that some the high-tech products would aware that the transformation and positively prepare the futural product producing and application. Thereby, the nations GDP will reflect the whole economy special in new high-tech-field maker and products will play a significant influence on that value increasement and control the y-y value under our consideration.

Keywords: *Searching for; analyzing; Chinese top cities; Mumbai & Chinese Zhejiang cities; by sustainably observing.*

1. Introduction

The nations & regions GDP (gross domestic product) will represent their comprehensive strength in views of economy level and quality, so searching it may have an important effectiveness for us to process statistic with the national producing amount every month, season and year. In the meantime, the value with y-y has also a significant meaning that reflects the economy growth step because we should clarify the increasing change so as to evaluate the increasement and declination value preciously. The positive y-y value may mean the good and rapid economy developing status whilst the minus one may state the bad and slow economy step. So we judge the economy developing enhancement and decreasement through that y-y value for a certain period. Thereby, the detail discussion will include in the following aspects. The GDP which indicates national economic status has provided an important role in every aspect in the world. So that the population increasing rate would be maintained for the sake of raising high-technique product with the entire industrial chain constantly which might enhance our new-quality-productivity. Hence we should consider the effective factors for example the population quantity, new quality productivity with high-technique etc. like big plane electric vehicle battery AI

robot, quantum computer, medicine making, disease diagnosis, AI (artificial intelligence), ocean source, space exploration, nuclear generator etc. other ones. Low population is able to offer high life & quality with improving GDP per capita value. Meanwhile, it can enhance the national whole GDP value and help us to boost the economic recovery and many things to do. So the certain population is about to improve our national confidence some degree and make us to become priority one as early as possible even the super-country to lead the world to leadership right.

In contrast, the GDP increasing rate may play a significant role with regulating population increasing rate mutually and cooperatively. Hence the two aspects may be emphasized and paid attention to in thriving the whole national economic developed degree through enough wielding our generations positively and efficiently by our government institution endeavor and evaluation. For the sake of making relevant policies and allocating capital into the necessary industries the corresponding strategic plan needs to be made under various background and entities. Then the according monitor and estimation will be followed and estimated periodically and frequently by the observer in government's institution. At last as to the developed speed in one nation the corresponding population increasing quantity and high-technique product producing will be discussed and considered more precious and correctly according to the near past years experience and variation.

Therefore, the high-technique products will be completed through wielding our scientist & senior Engineers coordination tightly for the sake of reviving the industrial and tertiary modernization. We should constantly look for and seek the new quality productivity sustainably so as to take place of our traditional industry becoming modernity. An innovation industry like new energy electric generator will be in front of our path forwards, so that the corresponding tactic must be put up and seek the opportunity and fortune in order to burden our responsibility quickly and not to forget recommend the fitting one to appoint new occupation. Like the Bole identified horse or Maosui self-recommended the recommendation will be represent one aspect for our human resource department to consider and evaluate the recommended included a full research room with a set of computer high-technique instrument & device, subordinate, subsidiary staff, salary, house, welfare etc. a series of work so as to appoint his new occupation reasonably and willingly. [1~16]

2. Discussions

For the sake of welcoming the demand we should educate a lot of scientist and experts candidates from university department to college & institution one to take the high scholar degree for them to grasp one foreign language and skill to apply to futural requirement and practice. In university, the class with taking more practice education and experience and good teacher proceed the more competition teaching and theoretical and practical combination class to prepare for using after their graduate from college. Meantime, the enhancing GDP factors will include the high-technique products and its whole industrial chains and high-intelligence product that may influence the service business mostly. So we should increase those high-profit & high-tech skill for making more advance products so as to improve our service business level and quality & effectiveness at all. So that we should maintain and develop the tertiary industry continuously under controlling the second one. With the life quality enhancing continually the service one is about to wield its effectiveness presently and in futural long time, thereby we should follow up the changed situation and own independent capacity to master one outstanding skill to satisfy the futural request in advance. [17~20]

2.1 Mumbai & Zhejiang province cities GDP analysis

The Mumbai & Zhejiang province cities GDP would show 6.4~6.9 billion dollars by Jinhua~Taizhou cities indicated the forward economy strength in terms of Figure 1 accordingly in 1988. The y-y value in 1988 might exhibit 26%~32% by them respectively showing their fastest growth step.

Figure 1. The Mumbai & Zhejiang province cities GDP. [1]

Meantime, the Mumbai & Zhejiang province cities GDP would show 7.5~13 billion dollars by Jiaying~Ningbo cities indicated the forward economy strength in terms of Figure 2 accordingly in 1988. The y-y value in 1988 might exhibit 22%~23% by them respectively showing their fastest growth step.

Figure 2. The Mumbai & Zhejiang province cities GDP I. [1]

Meantime, the Mumbai & Zhejiang province cities GDP would show 80~16 billion dollars by Jiaying~Ningbo cities indicated the forward economy strength in terms of Figure 3 accordingly in 1988. The y-y value in 1988 might exhibit 6%~19% by them respectively showing the Ningbo city faster growth step.

Figure 3. The Mumbai & Zhejiang province cities GDP II. [1]

1.2 Chinese top cities GDP analysis

The Chinese top cities GDP analysis 1.6~1.4 billion dollars by Guangzhou~Shenyang cities accordingly in 1984 exhibited their weak economy strength in light of Figure 4. The y-y value would indicate 28%~20% respectively realized their most forward growth steps.

Figure 4 The Chinese top cities GDP analysis [2]

Moreover, the Chinese top cities GDP analysis 6~3.5 billion dollars by Shanghai~Beijing cities accordingly in 1984 exhibited their strong economy strength in light of Figure 5. The y-y value would indicate 16%~20% respectively realized their more forward growth steps.

Figure 5 The Chinese top cities GDP analysis [2]

At the end, the Chinese top cities GDP analysis 1.3~1.1 billion dollars by Wuhan~Qingdao cities accordingly in 1984 exhibited their moderate economy strength in light of Figure 6. The y-y value would indicate 18%~8% respectively realized their forward growth steps.

Figure 6 The Chinese top cities GDP analysis I [2]

3. Conclusions

The nations & regions GDP (gross domestic product) will represent their comprehensive strength in views of economy level and quality, so searching it may have an important effectiveness for us to process statistic with the national producing amount every month, season and year. In the meantime, the value with y-y has also a significant meaning that reflects the economy growth step because we should clarify the increasing change so as to evaluate the increasement and declination value preciously. The positive y-y value may mean the good and rapid economy developing status whilst the minus one may state the bad and slow economy step. So we judge the economy developing enhancement and decreasement through that y-y value for a certain period. Meantime, the toughness of national economy developing force will be shown by the y-y value because some regions remained a low economy situation but its y-y value had high one explained the high toughness with such regions besides the low GDP value. So that the new-quality productivity will be sought by us continuously special by those scientist, senior engineer, experts because they can lead to new feasible energy and dynamic force to drive the new one into

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